

1 **Pcdh8 silencing during germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

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6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe Pcdh8 silencing during germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

10 Citations

11 1. Yu, J.S., Koujak, S., Nagase, S., Li, C.M., Su, T., Wang, X., Keniry, M., Memeo, L., Rojzman, A.,
12 Mansukhani, M. and Hibshoosh, H., 2008. PCDH8, the human homolog of PAPC, is a candidate tumor
13 suppressor of breast cancer. *Oncogene*, 27(34), pp.4657-4665.